

Group Name: Otter

Topic: Open Science Communities: Content strategy and visual content creation (an Otterly awesome guide)

Members:

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Topic: Open Science Communities: Content strategy and visual content creation (an Otterly awesome guide)

- Community engagement - You need a content strategy and visuals / visual content to make the members of a community feel engaged with the community, and to create a community identity.
- Community content creation / Visual content
- Content strategy
- Audience mapping / Tailored content - It is good to know your audience, when you know your audience, you can tailor your content towards your audience.
- Evolving growth: In your community, you have people from different research career stages, people within a community also evolve (from beginner researcher to more experienced researcher). While evolving as a researcher, you also might need to adjust your content within the community, so it stays tailored to your target group.

Desired outcome(s):

- Discuss and share tips and tricks for visuals
- Canva for content creation
- Communication tips: audience, content, and outcome.
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Inspirational materials and resources:

- Resource CSCCE: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cscce/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>
- LinkedIn posts:
 - https://ae.linkedin.com/posts/oscegypt_%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%85-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%88%D8%A7%D8%B7%D9%86-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%B1%D9%81%D8%A9-%D9%84%D9%85-%D8%AA%D8%B9%D8%AF-%D8%AA%D8%B5%D9%86%D8%B9-%D8%AF%D8%A7%D8%AE%D9%84-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%A7%D9%85%D9%84-activity-7450120230904881152-g67K?utm_source=li_share&utm_content=feedcontent&utm_medium=g_dt_web&utm_campaign=copy
 - https://ae.linkedin.com/posts/oscegypt_%D9%86%D8%B0%D9%83%D8%B1%D9%83

https://www.linkedin.com/feed/content/7427716038349176832-NBXc?utm_source=li_share&utm_content=feedcontent&utm_medium=g_dt_web&utm_campaign=copy

Notes:

- For visual content, Canva is a suggested tool. Users can build off existing work.
 - For content, a strategy is created months ahead.
 - Creating strategy:
 - Figure out what the problem is, and the goal is solving it.
 - Have recurrent meetings (3 months interval, or more) to evaluate communication strategy and improve.
 - What is content:
 - Anything that answers the 5Ws (who, what, when, why, where) and How
 - Information, clear update
 - About/for what is being done.‘
 - Something to raise awareness
 - Something that grabs attention
 - Make people feel like they belong
 - Forms of content:
 - Social media post, News items.
 - Publications
 - Content should match the vision and mission of a project/tool.
 - Short videos.
 - Community:
 - In-person communities
 - What is a community?
 - Community definition:
 - Shared goal
 - Connections and opportunity
 - Sense of belonging
- <https://www.cscce.org/>
- <https://medium.com/together-institute/introducing-the-community-weaving-framework-7679fe2d7216>
- Example: a service provider for a lot of communities, who has to interact with them, but isn't a community.
- What is the best way to make people feel connected if they only meet online within their community or network of communities?

- People within the same regions can meet at intervals.
- Community has different definitions, but a shared agreement is that it is people with the same goal. Different community audiences require various forms of engagement, and identifying your audience would enable you know the type of/method of content to create/share.
- Why do IRL events have more engagement:
 - It feels more personal, and people can easily respond. Also, public posts on groups have lesser responses to personalised asks.
 - It follows the principle that if you're talking to everybody, you're talking to no one.
- What is engagement?
 - Related to the mission
 - Usage
 - Collaboration
 - Feedback
 - Report
 - Recognition, reconnection
 - Questions
 - Following the rhythm of the community (engaging in meetups, communicating)
- Audience:
 - Some environments/countries have restricted access to tools. In identifying your audience, it is important to figure out the tools and modes of communication that work well for the environment.
 - Zulip as chat platform (sidenote: Zulip guide if you are interested: <https://zenodo.org/records/18624145>), an alternative to Slack. <https://zulip.com/>
 - The Turing Way: <https://book.the-turing-way.org/>

Split into two groups

- Strategy - <https://medium.com/together-institute/introducing-the-community-weaving-framework-7679fe2d7216>
- <https://community-canvas.org/>
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 - Target audience + community connection (bringing people together)

Challenges

Working on strategy:

- how can we bring people together in a community.
- how to make them feel engaged.
- How can we hold the community together as a group - especially if it is an online community - how to make people feel connected (in the long term).
- How to keep the people in the community - also when the community evolves and/or the people inside the community evolves (example from earlier researcher to experienced researcher).

Working on visual content:

- Quick tip - ure
- ...

Work in progress - Strategy group:

- Starting with defining challenges
 - Lack of engagement
- After that, coming up with solutions

4 stages of a community:

<https://osc-international.com/start-your-own-osc/>

1. Prepare and launch
2. Grow and inspire
3. Foster and maintain
4. Dream and scheme

Visit our OSC Starter Kit at www.StartYourOSC.com

THE FOUR STAGES OF DEVELOPING AN OPEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY

CSCCE

(https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353005411_Towards_Equitable_Diverse_and_Inclusive_science_collaborations_The_Multimessenger_Diversity_Network):

Target Audience ideas:

- Masters, PhD students

- Early career researchers
- Academic staff (professors)
- Data scientists
- Data managers
- Librarians
- Healthcare professionals

Challenge related to audience: always evolving and progressing throughout their careers

- Keep the people who have a lot of knowledge (while making it worthwhile for them)
- Continue to attract new
 - Suggested solution: mentorship

Country policy makes it hard to sometimes make initiatives official and to have sustainable funding

- Funding can sometimes be allocated to individuals/universities, not the community as a whole, so it requires individuals to within the community to often work on a voluntary basis

Target Audience: Anyone interested in Open Science

Goal: Foster engagement and retention in Open Science Communities

Final outcome: 10 quick tips for content creation in open science communities.

- It should have the text, and also a visual representation like the image above.
- 70/30 ratio for in-reach and outreach.

This has been done by Group 4, a sub-group which worked on the visual representation of these tips: [OSPARK-Bootcamp-Workshop](#)

Topic: Open Science Communities: Content strategy and visual content creation

Initial Version:

Challenge	Desired outcome	How to achieve outcome/overcome challenge
<p><u>Creating a community:</u> How can we bring people into a community?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It should be easy for people to join the community. 2. It should be understandable for new community members what is expected of them. 3. Make sure that your ambassadors and community members can talk about your community in 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Having a website or GitHub page. - An easy and clear way for people to join. - Your community should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. <p><i>(findable and accessible = mostly for 'how to bring people into the community'. Interoperable and reusable = mostly for 'how to bring people within a community</i></p>

	<p>an engaging way, so that they know how to bring in new people into the community.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New volunteers need to prepare a 'pitch' so they can talk about the community <p>4. Make the community visible</p>	<p><i>together / engagement')</i></p> <p>Interoperable = ensure your content can be exported in different formats, it can be used on any device (mobile, computer)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Clear contribution guide (example: Contributing to The Turing Way) 3. Reusable templates for current members to promote the community to potential/future members. 4. Have materials available (SWAG) to attract attention and make people feel special
<p><u>Community engagement:</u> How to make the community members feel engaged?</p> <p>How can we bring people together in a community?</p>	<p>It should be easy for all the members (including the new members) to use the community resources.</p> <p>Easy to use and reuse relevant materials for community members.</p> <p>Ensure that people within the community are updated about what happens within the community, and how they can actively engage.</p> <p>Review engagement and understand your community's interests.</p>	<p>Reusable templates for current members to promote the community</p> <p>Clear communication channels and guidelines (Slack, Zulip) for members.</p> <p>Recurring events: conferences/meetings, awards/recognition/incentives</p> <p>Newsletters with calls to action. Engaging section headers (April newsletter vs catchy header that encompasses newsletter - dependent on audience)</p> <p>Consistency in the posting on Social Media - so that people will know beforehand when a new post will come (managing expectations). Consistent exposure to the community. Example: every Wednesday at .. o' clock. (same day of the week, same time). Social data analytics tool: https://www.hubspot.com/</p> <p>Example: at an event, post something every day of the conference (overview</p>

		<p>of the day) and at the end of the conference (recap of the conference).</p> <p>Instagram stories (usually saved for 24 hours) - with question box so then if attendees have more questions after presentations, they can post questions there.</p> <p>Create a # for conferences and say that people can make pictures with this specific #. At the end people can win a gift when they use this # to promote the event.</p> <p>Review post metrics to guide future content and posting strategies.</p> <p>How to review engagement: ask community members every half-year/year/ (after a specific time) to review their own engagement, based on the contribution guide, and adjust their engagement accordingly. This helps to keep track of the state of your own community (how many 'active' members, how many 'semi-active' members etc.), and also helps the community leads to know how to proceed with establishing/increasing community engagement.</p>
<p><u>Retention</u> (keeping, holding, preserving the community): How can we hold the community together as a group - especially if it is an online community and has some geo-restrictions</p>	<p>Building a community that is engaged, enjoys working together, and feels connected to the group.</p>	<p>Give people the flexibility and resources to take on initiatives.</p> <p>Developing leadership positions, roles that depend on individuals contribution, accountability.</p> <p>Build systems to ensure recognition for contributions.</p>

<p>How to make people feel connected (in the long term).</p>		<p>Clear role definition and contribution progression opportunities. (explorer, contributor, maintainer, group leader, foundation fellow etc.). This could also be linked to the contribution guidelines.</p> <p>Establish a 'buddy', pair mentoring, or working group to allow for collaboration, inspiring each other, growing together and networking.</p> <p><u>Geolocation</u>: Time zone and language considerations</p> <p><u>Geolocation</u>: for organising events - keep in mind that working days and holidays may differ. Example: Work weeks in Arab countries are Sunday-Thursday. Work weeks in European countries / US are Monday-Friday. Potentially best days for group meetings Monday-Thursday.</p>
<p><u>Community evolvement and progression</u>: How to keep the people in the community? How to keep the community relevant for its members over time?</p> <p>A. When the community evolves (from a start-up to a well established community) -</p> <p>B. When the people inside the community evolve (example from 'beginner/inexperience d' with Open Science to 'experienced/knowledgeable' with Open Science' or from an earlier researcher to</p>	<p>Making sure a community continues to grow, instead of collapse/implodes after experienced people leave.</p> <p>Knowledge/experience should stay within the community.</p>	<p><u>When the community evolves</u>:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remember that the community is for your members. - Be aware of trends and adapt the community to these trends (e.g. hackathons, 'office hours' where technical leads to problem solve with members and share learnt experience) - Adjust or change social media platforms that you use, depending on how your community evolves. - Establish a way for the community to communicate (WhatsApp, Slack) - Make sure that administrative processes are in place, organize your files/data/presentations/etc. - Governance structure - Steering committee - Onboarding documents (for new members, for board members, for sub-groups etc.) - Making an overview document

<p>an experienced researcher).</p> <p><i>Offboarding how to support the transition into another community and show them what else is out there to support them.</i></p> <p><i>How do we retain people who have been around for a while this knowledge and ongoing engagement?</i></p>		<p>with info about how the community developed (start-up, what are the struggles that existed in the beginning, how to deal with these struggles, information on experiences).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offering meetings to potential new communities / other groups with the same sort of interest - to allow for learning opportunities. Share experiences, showing the learning process/learning curve as a well established community to likeminded start-ups. - Creating opportunities for collaboration with anyone who is interested in this topic (thinking of other initiatives or groups with similar interests). <p><u>When the people evolve:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Listen to the people within the community. - Find a middle ground. - Ask people what they need during their research journey (what sort of workshops, what sort of activities, etc.). - Ensure there are many opportunities to provide feedback - Don't just ask, but act. - Experienced members can be allocated as facilitators to help inform new members and share their expertise (this could be useful to experienced members to identify knowledge gaps) - Ensure there are ways to publish the work that is being developed within the community (this might especially be relevant / to interest for experienced members in the community). - Potentially have special events
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		<p>for experienced members/experts where they can have in-depth discussions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable experienced members of the community to work together on funding opportunities and grant application processes within the community.
<p><u>Balancing sharing information without information overload</u> How do we ensure that we are producing quality content, not just to hit quantity quotas.</p>	<p>Find the right balance to ensure people get the information they need to know about your community, and at the same time making sure they don't feel overloaded with information (that can cause them to not read the info anymore, unsubscribe to newsletters or stop following instagram/facebook groups etc.)</p>	<p>Consistency of posting - developing a schedule.</p> <p>Encouraging community members to share themselves. Call for action for community members to share publicly themselves.</p> <p>Reviewing engagement on posts to understand what the community enjoys, or what is not as well received</p> <p><u>Facebook:</u> Using push notifications on facebook. You need to pay a small amount of money, and then your message will be shown on more people's timeline and will get higher on people's timelines.</p> <p><u>Slack/Facebook:</u> use the option to 'pin' important messages, or videos describing the purpose of the community, at the top of people's timelines.</p> <p>Having meetings with volunteers and other community members to understand what type of content is needed, or would be helpful.</p>
<p><u>Inclusion</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Different career stages: Early career researchers (undergraduates, PhD, Postdoc) versus established career 	<p>Ensure content is accessible to all abilities.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create an open environment where all feel welcome to contribute and participate. For example: Write invitations for events in an open and engaging way, so 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In management/leadership committees, ensure that there is a balance between genders and also career stages. <p>Live translator or captions for online calls.</p> <p>Developing content in 2 languages</p>

<p>researchers (professors etc.)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Gender inclusion Language inclusion: How to deal with language barriers within your community? <p>Practical issue: If you write in English (reading from left to right) and Arabic (reading from right to left), some online text platforms have issues with this. They automatically make all the text aligned to the left margin.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Geolocation: Taking into consideration that there are differences between countries in access to resources (example: no (fast) internet access in all rural areas in developing countries; low resource environment) Accessibility limitations (example: visual or auditory impairment, physical impairments) 	<p>everyone feels welcome and included.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Create an open environment where all feel welcome to contribute and participate. Communicate in the countries main language and in English (example: Arabic and English) <p>Creating a safe environment for all community members.</p>	<p>(promotional materials - like flyers, event info on the website, etc.)</p> <p>Post content in two separate posts, as this ensures that each group receives the information, without having to click 'See more'.</p> <p>Open calls to leading meetings, so that it is not always one person or one 'type' of person.</p> <p><u>Example:</u> The events are open to everyone [living in ... area, or, working at or affiliated with ... research institute/university <i>[depending on the situation in your particular region]</i>]. We welcome all researchers, educational professionals, staff, RDM professionals, and others with an interest in Open Science, from all university levels. The events are informal and inclusive, so feel welcome to join and participate in our interesting discussions!</p> <p>Make use of accessible tools and platforms (Framapad instead of Google Docs), .md file formats, consider fonts and colours used, images have alt text to allow for screen reading. Ensure that systems are put in place to accommodate accessibility from the planning phase, do not let this be an afterthought.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure we use tools that require low bandwidth. Encourage asynchronous communication. <p>Events: Ensure that in person events have considerations for accessibility. To assist with this, include information about special needs in the event registration.</p>
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Final version:

Challenge	Desired Outcome	How to Achieve / Calls to Action
1. Creating a Community: How can we bring people into a community?		
It should be easy for people to join the community.	New members can find and join the community with minimal friction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a website or GitHub page. • Provide an easy and clear way for people to join. • Ensure your community is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (findable and accessible = mostly for bringing people into the community). • Interoperable = ensure your content can be exported in different formats and used on any device (mobile, computer).
It should be understandable for new community members what is expected of them.	New members understand how to participate and contribute from the start.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a clear contribution guide (example: Contributing to The Turing Way).
Ambassadors and community members need to talk about the community in an engaging way, so they know how to bring in new people.	The community is visible and actively promoted by its members.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New volunteers need to prepare a 'pitch' so they can talk about the community. • Provide reusable templates for current members to promote the community to potential/future members. • Have materials available (SWAG) to attract attention and make people feel special.
2. Community Engagement: How to make the community members feel engaged?		
It should be easy for all members (including new members) to use the community resources.	Easy to use and reuse relevant materials for community members.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide reusable templates for current members to promote the community. • Clear communication channels and guidelines (Slack, Zulip) for members.
Ensure that people within the community are updated about what happens and how they can actively engage.	Members stay informed and have regular opportunities to participate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recurring events: conferences/meetings, awards/recognition/incentives. • Newsletters with calls to action. • Engaging section headers (e.g. catchy header that encompasses newsletter content – dependent on audience).

Challenge	Desired Outcome	How to Achieve / Calls to Action
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency in Social Media posting – so people know when a new post will come (managing expectations). Example: every Wednesday at a set time. • Social data analytics tool: https://www.hubspot.com/ • At events, post something every day (overview of the day) and at the end (recap of the conference). • Instagram stories (saved for 24 hours) – with question box so attendees can post questions after presentations. • Create a # for conferences and encourage people to use it. At the end, people can win a gift for using the # to promote the event.
<p>How to review engagement and understand community interests.</p>	<p>Content and posting strategies are guided by data and member feedback.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review post metrics to guide future content and posting strategies. • Ask community members every half-year/year to review their own engagement, based on the contribution guide, and adjust accordingly. • This helps track the state of the community (how many 'active' vs 'semi-active' members) and helps community leads know how to proceed with increasing engagement.
<p>3. Retention: How can we hold the community together as a group?</p>		
<p>How to make people feel connected (in the long term), especially if it is an online community with some geo-restrictions.</p>	<p>Building a community that is engaged, enjoys working together, and feels connected to the group.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give people the flexibility and resources to take on initiatives. • Develop leadership positions and roles that depend on individuals' contributions and accountability. • Build systems to ensure recognition for contributions. • Clear role definition and contribution progression opportunities (explorer, contributor, maintainer, group leader, foundation fellow, etc.). This could be linked to the contribution guidelines. • Establish a 'buddy', pair mentoring, or working group to allow for collaboration, inspiring each other, growing together and networking. • Geolocation: Time zone and language considerations. • Geolocation: For organising events – keep in mind that working days and holidays may differ. Example: Work weeks in Arab countries are Sunday–Thursday. Work weeks in European countries/US are Monday–Friday. Potentially best days for group meetings: Monday–Thursday.
<p>4. Community Evolvement and Progression: How to keep the community relevant over time?</p>		
<p>When the community evolves (from a start-up</p>	<p>The community adapts and continues to grow; knowledge and experience</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remember that the community is for your members.

Challenge	Desired Outcome	How to Achieve / Calls to Action
to a well-established community).	stay within the community. Administrative and governance structures are in place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of trends and adapt the community (e.g. hackathons, 'office hours' where technical leads problem-solve with members). • Adjust or change social media platforms depending on how the community evolves. • Establish a way for the community to communicate. Choose a platform they're already familiar with (WhatsApp, Slack). • Ensure administrative processes are in place; organise files/data/presentations. • Establish a governance structure and steering committee. • Create onboarding documents (for new members, board members, sub-groups, etc.). • Create an overview document with info about how the community developed (start-up, struggles, how to deal with them, experiences). • Offer meetings to potential new communities/groups with the same interest – to share experiences and learning curves. • Create opportunities for collaboration with anyone interested in this topic (other initiatives or groups with similar interests).
When the people inside the community evolve (e.g. from 'beginner' to 'experienced' with Open Science, or from early career to experienced researcher).	Members continue to find value in the community as they progress. Experienced members stay engaged and share knowledge. Offboarding supports smooth transitions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listen to the people within the community. • Find a middle ground. • Ask people what they need during their research journey (workshops, activities, etc.). • Ensure there are many opportunities to provide feedback. • Don't just ask, but act. • Experienced members can be allocated as facilitators to help inform new members and share their expertise (this also helps experienced members identify knowledge gaps). • Ensure there are ways to publish the work developed within the community (this may especially interest experienced members). • Potentially have special events for experienced members/experts with in-depth discussions. • Enable experienced members to work together on funding opportunities and grant applications within the community. • Offboarding: support the transition into another community and show them what else is out there.

5. Balancing Information Sharing Without Information Overload

Challenge	Desired Outcome	How to Achieve / Calls to Action
<p>How to ensure quality content without just hitting quantity quotas. Finding the right balance so people get the information they need without feeling overloaded (which can cause them to unsubscribe or stop following).</p>	<p>Community members receive relevant, high-quality information in a manageable way.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency of posting – develop a schedule. • Encourage community members to share themselves. Call for action for community members to share publicly. • Review engagement on posts to understand what the community enjoys, or what is not well received. • Facebook: Use push notifications (small payment required) so messages are shown on more people’s timelines. • Slack/Facebook: Use the option to ‘pin’ important messages, or videos describing the purpose of the community, at the top of timelines. • Have meetings with volunteers and community members to understand what type of content is needed or helpful.
<h2>6. Inclusion</h2>		
<p>Different career stages: Early career researchers (undergraduates, PhD, Postdoc) versus established career researchers (professors, etc.).</p>	<p>All career stages feel welcome to contribute and participate.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In management/leadership committees, ensure a balance between genders and career stages. • Open calls to leading meetings, so it is not always one person or one ‘type’ of person. • Write invitations for events in an open and engaging way, so everyone feels welcome and included. • Example text: “The events are open to everyone [living in ... area, or working at/affiliated with ... research institute/university]. We welcome all researchers, educational professionals, staff, RDM professionals, and others with an interest in Open Science, from all university levels. The events are informal and inclusive, so feel welcome to join and participate in our interesting discussions!”
<p>Gender inclusion.</p>	<p>Creating a safe environment for all community members.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In management/leadership committees, ensure that there is a balance between genders. • Create an open environment where all feel welcome to contribute and participate.
<p>Language inclusion: How to deal with language barriers within the community? Practical issue: If you write in English (left to right) and Arabic (right to left), some online text platforms automatically align all text to the left margin.</p>	<p>Content is accessible in multiple languages and formats.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate in the country’s main language and in English (example: Arabic and English). • Develop content in 2 languages (promotional materials, flyers, event info on website, etc.). • Post content in two separate posts, so each group receives the information without having to click ‘See more’. • Live translator or captions for online calls.
<p>Geolocation: Differences between countries in</p>	<p>Community resources are usable in low-bandwidth</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure we use tools that require low bandwidth.

Challenge	Desired Outcome	How to Achieve / Calls to Action
access to resources (e.g. no fast internet access in rural areas in developing countries; low resource environments).	and low-resource environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage asynchronous communication.
Accessibility limitations (e.g. visual or auditory impairment, physical impairments).	Content is accessible to all abilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make use of accessible tools and platforms (Framapad instead of Google Docs), .md file formats. • Consider fonts and colours used; images have alt text to allow for screen reading. • Ensure systems are put in place to accommodate accessibility from the planning phase – do not let this be an afterthought. • For in-person events, have considerations for accessibility. • Include information about special needs in event registration.

Example Instagram story line: The photo was posted o Instagram during presenting in Egyptian conference to get people attention and asking them about their opinions in the presentation and if they have any suggestions to the OSCEgypt community

 Linktr.ee

Example of a pinned/linked post on facebook/insta:

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/oscegypt_%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%8A%D9%88%D9%85-%D9%86%D8%AD%D8%AA%D9%81%D9%84-%D8%A8%D9%85%D8%B1%D9%88%D8%B1-%

Visual content

We created a mindmap for visual content creation:

Tips for multimedia content creation

Digital accessibility is
for everyone !!
Not optional

inclusive
words

works
on
low
bandwidth

colour
contrast

font
size &
type

Alt
text

CC

Use
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icons

cc by
images

What platform?
 What pasting
 consistency?

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posters

email

every
 wednesday,

12 noon
 UTC

We created a mindmap for visual content creation:

Tips for multimedia content creation

First things first: If you have the funds, consider involving a graphic designer (find eg via fiver, in your own organization), (fill in other things you can buy)

- Make sure they understand audience and brand!

Types

- Images
- Video
- Text
- audio

Message - What do I want to say

- Invite people to join the community
- News
- Events
- Milestones
- Educational / Informational

- New resources / Deliverables
- ** Community spotlight/ champions highlights
- ** Opinions / Editorials

Considerations for your message: one or many visuals/posts; relate things to scope of initiative, personalise/humanizs, cross promotion

Tools

- Microsoft office / Open/Libre Office: Powerpoint, Excel
- Canva
- GenAI such as Claude, gemini, chatgpt
- [Draw.io](https://draw.io)
- Figma - <https://www.figma.com/>
- Inkscape - Illustrator
- Gimp - Photoshop
- Programming (mermaid, ...)
- Pen and paper -> digitize

Skills -> depends on the content you want to make.

- Youtube
- Courses
- Blogposts
- Mentoring
- ...

Target audience

Creator

Community-created content

- Incentivise, motivation (repost, comment/ engagement -> reach)
- Physical manifestation of community
- Call to action: Provide context, scaffolding, templates, questions, user journeys
Addressing user needs via feedback forms, polls
- Awards
- Hackathon

Single author / Community manager, Outreach person

Accessibility

- Alt texts for images
- captions/transcripts
- Readable fonts/sizes
- Colour contrast
- Inclusive language
- Device and bandwidth friendly

Sources of visual elements

- Icons - iconbuddy, <https://iconmonstr.com/>
- Images - [Pixabay](#), [Pexels](#), [Wikimedia commons](#), [Unsplash](#)
- Videos - [Pixabay](#), [Pexels](#), Aggregators like [AllTheFreeStock](#)
- GenAI
- Gifs - [Pixabay](#), [GIPHY](#)
- Sounds - Freesound, Pixabay, [Epidemic Sound](#)

Note: Check License! -> CC0 ideally

Platforms

Physical platforms

Types:

- Posters
- Merch (stickers, totes, tshirts)
- Brochures
- Catalogs
- Business cards
- Flyers

Consider: Evergreen content

Places/events:

- Un-/conferences
- Works
- Roadshow/promopromo event
- "Infiltration" / opportunity events
- Job/Student events
- Community-related events'

Digital platforms

- where is your target audience (physically and digitally),
- what language do they speak (English, etc., but also formal/informal, etc.)

- Availability of platforms (eg some countries have restrictions)
- Own website (static and dynamic)
- Community chat
 - Zulip, Slack, Rocketchat, Mattermost, ..
- Social media
 - LinkedIn, Instagram, TicToc, Mastodon, Bluesky, Facebook, ...
 - Dynamic / temporal
- Other websites (like Medium, ...)
- Registries, Networks, Consortia, Clusters, Aggregators

Permanence, Persistence (static vs dynamic, temporal)

Static material to go on the website

Dynamic material to go on social, etc.

Rhythm

- On time: When events/milestones etc happen
- Ongoing: Once in a while, invitations, community overview and story, educational
- Scheduled: News, milestones
- In sync with the algorithm
- In sync with community time- and deadlines
- Consistency (every Wednesday at xx:yy hour, etc)

5 W's: Who, What, When, Why, Where

Process of getting to the summary image:

1. Brainstorming to get to a mind map (pen and paper 2h+)

2. Expanding each "leaf" with thoughts connected to it
 TODO: pictures here

3. Take clear photos of all your pages, or select the ones you want to develop further. These will be used as input for the next stage.
4. Upload the images into a tool like Claude, or upload one image and paste the rest of your notes. Use this step to organise your ideas, group related content, and generate a first structured draft.
5. Take that draft into ChatGPT and refine it further by improving clarity, flow, and wording. You can also add any extra content you may have left out earlier to strengthen the final output.
6. Use the refined content to create your visual or zine. Sketch the layout, translate the ideas into a handwritten and visual format, and iterate until it feels clear and easy to follow.

① FIRST THINGS FIRST

If you have the funds, consider involving people who can **level it up**.

- graphic designer
- illustrator
- video editor
- accessibility reviewer
- copywriter
- photographer

Make sure they understand:
YOUR AUDIENCE + YOUR BRAND!
(aka the vibe ✨:)

② MESSAGE

WHAT AM I TRYING TO SAY?

- invite people in
- share news
- announce events
- celebrate milestones
- teach something
- share resources
- highlight people (community spotlight!)
- opinions / editorial

REMEMBER:

- one post or many?
- fit your community scope
- make it human!
- cross-promote smartly

③ TYPES OF CONTENT

images video text audio

Mix them up → make it multimedia magic!

④ TOOLS

- PowerPoint / Excel
- Canva
- Figma
- draw.io
- Inkscape / Illustrator
- Gimp / Photoshop
- GenAI
- code (mermaid, etc.)
- pen & paper → digitize

TOOLS DON'T MAKE GOOD CONTENT. THINKING DOES.

⑤ SKILLS (YOU DON'T NEED ALL AT ONCE!)

- creativity
- design basics
- storytelling
- technical skills

HOW TO LEARN:

- YouTube
- courses
- blogposts
- mentoring
- community

Start simple: use simple shapes, lines, circles, triangles and squares. Use templates that are comfortable for you.

⑥ AUDIENCE & CREATORS

TARGET AUDIENCE vs **CREATOR**

Who is this for? No really — **WHO?**

COMMUNITY-CREATED CONTENT

- Encourage participation
- Repost & engage → builds reach
- Make the community visible

HELP PEOPLE CONTRIBUTE:

- templates
- prompts
- examples
- clear CTAs

IDEAS: AWARDS, HACKATHONS, SHOWCASES

⑦ ACCESSIBILITY (NOT OPTIONAL)

- alt text for images
- captions / transcripts
- readable fonts & sizes
- good colour contrast
- inclusive language
- works on low bandwidth

IF PEOPLE CAN'T ACCESS IT → IT DOESN'T EXIST.

⑧ SOURCES FOR VISUAL ELEMENTS (DON'T REINVENT EVERYTHING)

- icons → iconbuddy
- images → Pixabay, Pexels, Wikimedia Commons
- videos → Pixabay, Pexels, AllTheFreeStock
- gifs → various libraries
- Sounds → Freesound, Pixabay
- GenAI → use responsibly

CHECK LICENSES!

Aim for **CCO / PUBLIC DOMAIN**

⑨ PLATFORMS

PHYSICAL PLATFORMS

- posters
- merch (stickers, totes, t-shirts)
- brochures / catalogs
- business cards
- flyers

DIGITAL PLATFORMS

Ask yourself:

- where is your audience?
- what language do they speak?
- what formats do they like?

WHERE?

- conferences
- works / campuses
- roadshows / promo events
- opportunity events
- community-related events

Think: evergreen content!

⑩ TIME & RHYTHM

STATIC vs DYNAMIC

STATIC (evergreen) → website, long-term

DYNAMIC → social, fast-moving

RHYTHM MATTERS

- ON TIME → events, milestones
- ONGOING → storytelling, invites
- SCHEDULED → news, updates

Also in sync with:

- algorithms (ugh)
- community time & deadlines

CONSISTENCY

Pick something realistic. Better small + consistent than big + once.

WED 12:00

GOOD VISUAL CONTENT ISN'T ABOUT BEING PERFECT. IT'S ABOUT BEING: **CLEAR** **HUMAN** **USEFUL** **CONSISTENT**

... and sometimes just starting anyway. ✨ You've got this! ♥

8 things to go on 8 pages of zine:

Mascot - Otter

Reason - Otters are highly social, playful, and curious animals

Awesome Otter's Story

Hi, I am 'Awesome Otter' - I am highly social and curious and want to help you in your community-building journey.

A picture speaks a thousand words.

Turn over to get to know about the pillars of **effective visual communication**.

1. Introduction of Awesome (## draw picute of Awesome Otter, write that the Otter is 'I am your curious and social friend. I want to take you on a tour to help you build your community)
2. What is your message? (## draw icon of speech bubble, loudspeaker) Which multimedia content do you want to make? (## draw icons of multimedia)
3. Got some funds? Try having a team
4. Tools to use & Skills
5. Who is your audience, and who are the creators
6. Digital Accessibility elevates everyone's experience; it's not optional!
7. Use existing sources for the visual element; do not start from scratch
8. What Platforms and posting consistency do you want

Video generation: <https://instadoodle.com/>

Topic	Key considerations	How to / Resources
1. Getting started		
First things first	If you have funds, bring in specialists who understand your audience and brand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphic designer (Fiverr, your organisation) • Illustrator • Video editor • Accessibility reviewer • Copywriter / photographer <p><i>Make sure they understand your audience + brand!</i></p>
2. What to make		
Types of content	Mix formats to reach different audiences and create multimedia impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Images • Video • Text • Audio
Message	What do you want to say? Consider: one or many visuals/posts; relate to scope; personalise/humanise; cross-promote.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invite people to join • News / Events / Milestones • Educational / Informational • New resources / Deliverables • Community spotlight / champion highlights • Opinions / Editorials
3. Tools & skills		
Tools	Choose tools that match your skills and content type. Tools don't make good content — thinking does.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PowerPoint / Excel / LibreOffice • Canva • GenAI (Claude, Gemini, ChatGPT) • Draw.io, Figma • Inkscape / Illustrator • GIMP / Photoshop • Programming (Mermaid, ...) • Pen and paper → digitise
Skills	Depends on the content you want to make. You don't need everything at once — start simple.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity, design basics, storytelling, technical skills • Learn via: YouTube, courses, blogposts, mentoring, community • Use simple shapes: circles, triangles, squares • Use templates you're comfortable with
4. Audience & creators		
Target audience & creator	Who is this for — really? Single author, community manager, or outreach person?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define your audience clearly before creating • Single author vs. community manager vs. outreach person
Community-created content	Involve the community to build reach, ownership, and visibility.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentivise and motivate (repost, comment, engagement) • Provide templates, prompts, questions, user journeys • Address needs via feedback forms and polls • Awards, hackathons, showcases

